

TRAFFIC PERCEPTION BASED ON WEATHER CONDITION

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Abstract:

— Traffic accidents are particularly serious on the rainy days, the dark nights, the rainy nights, the foggy day, and many other times with low visibility conditions. Existing vision driver assistance systems are designed to perform under good-natured weather conditions. Classification is a type of methodology to identify the optical characteristics for vision enhancement algorithms to make them more efficient. To improve the machine vision at bad weather situations, a multi-class weather classification method has been presented based on multiple weather features and supervised learning. Priorly underlying visual features are extracted from multi-traffic scene images. Then secondly, five supervised learning algorithms are used to train classifiers. The analysis shows about how extracted features can accurately describe the image semantics, and classifiers have high recognition accuracy rate and adaptive ability. The proposed method will be providing the basis for further enhancing the detection of anterior vehicle detection during the night time illumination changes, and enhancing the driver's field of vision on a foggy day.

Keywords — Machine Learning, Unsupervised Learning, Python, Digital Image Processing, Support Vector Machine Algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

Highway traffic accidents bring huge losses to people's based skyline detection algorithm under image brightness lives and property. The advanced driver assistance system variations propose automatic traffic data columns (ADAS) play a significant role in reducing traffic accidents under varying lighting conditions. Multi-traffic scene perception of complex weather use classifiers for detecting road areas under multi-traffic conditions is a piece of valuable information for assistance scenes. Wang et al. propose multi-vehicle detection and systems. Based on different weather categories, a specialized tracking system it is evaluated by

roadway-captured approaches can be used to improve visibility. This will contribute to a variety of illumination and weather conditions, and will expand the application of ADAS. Satzoda and Trivedi propose a vehicle detection method.

Research has been done on weather-related issues for seven various datasets that captured varying road, traffic, and in-vehicle camera systems so far. Payne and Singh propose weather conditions. classifying both the indoor and the outdoor images by edge intensity.

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

Highway traffic accidents cause huge losses to human's lives and property. Advanced driver assistants (ADAS) play very important role in reducing traffic accidents.

- The multi-traffic display of complex weather conditions is valuable information for helping companies. Specific approaches can be used to improve visibility based on different weather conditions. This will contribute to the expansion of ADAS. There has been little work on neither-related issues for automotive cameras so far. Classification of interior and exterior images through the margin intensity. Concentration curves form four fog levels by a neural network. Providing a novel structure to recognize different climates.
- Current view-based localization and mapping in altering external environments. Find important changes Driving is an important task during driving Help Systems. propose a sight-based skyline Finding the algorithms under picture brightness variations Fu and AI. Automatic traffic data collection varies in Lighting conditions. Classes to use Detecting road segments in many traffic scenes.

III . PROPOSED SYSTEM

Image feature extraction is an important step of supervised learning. It is divided into global feature extraction and local feature extraction. Multi-traffic scene perception is more concerned about global features, such as color distribution, texture features outdoor conditions. Propose a night image enhancement method in order to improve nighttime driving and reduce rear-end accidents. Present an effective nighttime vehicle detection system based on image enhancement. Present an image enhancement algorithm for low-light scenes in an environment with insufficient illumination. Propose an image fusion technique to improve imaging quality in low-light shooting. Propose a vehicle detection method on seven different weather images that captured varying road, traffic, and weather conditions. To reduce the traffic and accident issues.

IV. RESULTS

V. CONCLUSION

Weather recognition based on road images is a brand-new and challenging subject, which is widely required in many fields. Hence, research of weather recognition based on images is in urgent demand, which can be used to recognize the weather conditions for many vision systems. Classification is a methodology to identify the type of optical characteristics for vision enhancement algorithms to make them more efficient. In this paper, eight global underlying visual features are extracted and five supervised learning algorithms are used to perceive multi-traffic road scene. Firstly, our method extracts colour features, texture features and boundary feature which are used to evaluate the image quality. Thus, the extracted features are more comprehensive. Secondly, the ten categories traffic scene image are marked as labels 1-10. Owing to the category label represents the whole image, there is no need to mark the specific area or key point of image. Thirdly, by using of five supervised learning that mentioned in Section IV, we can greatly simplify the manual annotation process of feature sample and improve the classifier efficiency. At last, experiments and comparisons are performed on large datasets to verify the effectiveness of the proposed method in Section V. It proved that the proposed eight features not only can accurately describe image characteristics, but also have strong robustness and stability at the complex weather environment and the ELM algorithm is superior to other algorithms.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Milford, E. Vig, W. Scheirer, and D. Cox, "Vision-based simultaneous localization and mapping in changing outdoor environments," *J. Field Robot.*, vol.
- [2] C.-Y. Fang, S.-W. Chen, and C.-S. Fuh, "Automatic change detection of driving environments in a vision-based driver assistance system," *IEEE Trans.*
- [3] Y. J. Liu, C. C. Chiu, and J. H. Yang, "A robust vision-based skyline detection algorithm under different weather conditions,"
- [4] K. Wang, Z. Huang, and Z. Zhong, "Simultaneous multi-vehicle detection and tracking framework with pavement constraints based on machine learning and particle filter algorithm,".